

Role of Yoga in Management of Lifestyle

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Abstract: Yoga is a traditional Indian practice that focuses equally on the evolution of the physical, mental, social, and spiritual levels to create a complete personality. Yoga, which consists of postures, controlled breathing, relaxation exercises, and Meditation, might enhance one's capacity to organize and perform a specific cognitive function. Studies have demonstrated that the amalgamation of yoga postures can improve motor speed, and cyclic meditation, which involves paying close attention, can enhance perception. Yoga is one of the six systems of Indian philosophy. It is one of the most ancient systems of psychosomatic training known to the human being who is bestowed by the seers and sages of india. Yoga has a great art and science of personality development even though it is the basic education system of the humanity. Positive healthy physical, mental, intellectual, emotional, social and spiritual health is an important means of leading meaningful life filled with happiness and inner harmony. Marshi Patanjali is great contribution to lead such a life through the principles and practices of ashtanga yoga. They include the aspects of human personality on explanation of Social behavior, personal traits like intellect and emotions as well as the connecting the prospective of mind and body for the state of perfect balance condition.

Keywords: Yoga, Aspects, Health. Personality development, Skill Development.

Introduction: Development of personality is an important issue. Personality starts developing since birth, but it assumes great importance during adolescence, when reorganisation of personality takes place. Personality is a very common term which is used in our day-to-day life. It tells us what type of person one is. We know that each person generally behaves consistently in most of the situations. The examples of this

consistency can be seen in a person who remains friendly or a person who is generally kind or helpful in most situations. Such a consistent pattern of behaviour is termed as personality. It can be called as the sum total of behaviour that includes attitudes, emotions, thoughts, habits and traits. This pattern of behaviour is characteristic to an individual. There are various dimensions of personality. These dimensions are related to physical, emotional, intellectual, social and spiritual aspects of our behaviour. For a holistic personality development, yoga plays an important role.

Objects of This Paper:

- 1) To know role of „Yoga“ in personality Development
- 2) To know and understand the personality development.
- 3) To know the Important Aspects of personality.

Discussion: Yoga and Personality Development: Yogic practices are found effective for development of all dimensions of personality. Let us talk about the yogic practices that influence development of different dimensions of personality. Yoga and Physical Dimension of Personality: Physical dimension is related to our body. It means that all organs and systems of our body should be properly developed and functions. It implies a healthy body without any disease. Yogic practices like asana, pranayama, and bandha play a beneficial role in physical development of children. There is a series of asanas and pranayamas which help to improve the functioning of the body. Yoga and Emotional Dimension of Personality: Yogic practices are effective for development of emotional dimension related to our feelings, attitudes and emotions. There are two kinds of emotions: positive and negative. For example love, kindness are positive emotions, while anger and fear (exam phobia) are negative emotions. Similarly, our feelings and attitudes may be positive and negative. For emotional development, positive feelings, attitudes and emotions should be developed and negative ones should be controlled, as the negative attitudes and emotions work as a mental block for the development of personality. Yoga plays a critical role in development of positive emotions. It brings emotional stability. It helps to control negative emotions. Yogic practices such as yama,

niyama, asana, pranayama, pratyahara and meditation help in emotional management. For example, the principle of non-violence will protect us from negative emotions and develop positive feelings of love and kindness. Similarly, other principles of yama and niyama will help to develop positive emotions and attitudes in our personal and social life and therefore help in the management of emotions. **Yoga and Intellectual Dimension of Personality:** Intellectual development is related to the development of our mental abilities and processes such as critical thinking, memory, perception, decision making, imagination, creativity, etc. Development of this dimension is very important as it enables us to learn new things and acquire knowledge and skills. Yogic practices such as asana, pranayama, dharana, dhyana (meditation) help to develop concentration, memory and thereby help in intellectual development. **Yoga and Social Dimension of Personality:** Primary socialisation, probably the most important aspect of the personality development takes place during infancy, usually within the family. By responding to the approval and disapproval of parents and grandparents and imitating their examples, the child learns the language and many of the basic behaviour patterns of her/his society. The process of socialisation is not limited to childhood, but continues throughout life and teach the growing child and adolescent about the norms and rules of the society in which she/he lives . Some key elements of this process include respect for others, listening carefully to other persons, being interested in them, and voicing your thoughts and feelings politely, honestly and clearly so that you can be easily heard and understood. Principles of yama include these key elements and are very important as these help us in the betterment of our relationships with our friends, parents, teachers and others.

Yoga and Spiritual Dimension of Personality: This dimension is related to the development of values. It is also concerned with self-actualisation which is related to recognising one's potential and developing them to the maximum. Proper development of this dimension helps the person to realise one's true identity. For spiritual development, yama, niyama, pratyahara and dhyana (meditation) are helpful. Yama and niyama help to develop our moral values while pranayama, and meditation help us to realise our true self. Introspection is very effective for the development of 'self'.

Role of Hatha Yoga in Personality Development: 1. Imbalance of physical and mental energies is state of disease. 2. Imbalance is due to blockages in the 'nadis' or energy passages. 3. Aim of Hath Yoga - Purification of this 'nadis' or energy passages.

Why we need develop the personality?

The following are the some of the benefits for personality.

- ❖ Build strong conviction.
- ❖ Creates willingness to accept responsibility.
- ❖ Builds optimistic attitude.
- ❖ Leads to better relationship and fulfilling lives.
- ❖ Makes a person more sensitive to other's need and develop a caring attitude.
- ❖ Makes a person self-motivated and ambitious.
- ❖ Makes a person open to new opportunities and challenges.
- ❖ Improve performance and increase risk taking ability.
- ❖ Helps a person give and receive both criticism and complements tactfully and easily

Conclusion: Based on the forgoing description, it can be concluded that the performance of human being can be explored at the highest level like Devine human being through the practices of regular yoga. It is therefore necessary to introduce this subject will attached from primary to university higher education; this will bring healthy, wealthy, happy and prosperous life to all of us.

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